

Milestone: M3.4: Strategy to identify the most critical parts of a workflow for optimisation

Lead Participant: VIB

Author: Rafael Andrade Buono (VIB) + report authors

Due: 31 July 2025 (18)

Date Of Completion: 31/07/2025

Means of Verification

[Report on Milestone 3.4](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Project participants & others

Rafael Andrade Buono (VIB)
Anna Golobardes, José M. Fernández, Anna Redondo (BSC)
Nicola Soranzo (Earlham)
Alexander Kanitz (SIB)
Heleri Inno (UT)
Marco Antonio Tangaro (CNR)
Members of Tasks 3.3 and 3.4

Next action steps

Further benchmarking of ELIXIR Communities contributed workflows, further enhancements to workflow management systems in job caching and utilization of smart scheduling

ELIXIR-STEERS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101131096.

